

Vitamin C is not a placebo equivalent

Harri Hemilä¹

This comment was originally published in PubPeer, 2021 March:

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/0100A772EC303AC9B0F62FDA030E32#1>

The address of this version is: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20303874>

Comment on:

Barnabas RV, Brown ER, Bershteyn A, Stankiewicz Karita HC, Johnston C, Thorpe LE, Kottkamp A, Neuzil KM, Laufer MK, Deming M, Paasche-Orlow MK, Kissinger PJ, Luk A, Paolino K, Landovitz RJ, Hoffman R, Schaafsma TT, Krows ML, Thomas KK, Morrison S, Haugen HS, Kidoguchi L, Wener M, Greninger AL, Huang ML, Jerome KR, Wald A, Celum C, Chu HY, Baeten JM; Hydroxychloroquine COVID-19 PEP Study Team.

Hydroxychloroquine as Postexposure Prophylaxis to Prevent Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 Infection : A Randomized Trial.

Ann Intern Med. 2021 Mar;174(3):344-352.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33284679>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7732017>

<https://doi.org/10.7326/M20-6519>

In their RCT to test hydroxychloroquine as postexposure prophylaxis to prevent SARS-CoV-2, Barnabas et al. used vitamin C as a placebo [1]: *“Households were randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to receive either hydroxychloroquine (400 mg/d orally for 3 days, then 200 mg/d orally for an additional 11 days) or ascorbic acid (500 mg/d orally for 3 days, then 250 mg/d orally for 11 days) as a placebo equivalent.”* [bold added]

Vitamin C is not a physiologically inactive substance.

Cochrane review on vitamin C for respiratory virus infections reported that 31 comparisons examined the effect of regular vitamin C on the duration of 9745 episodes. In adults the duration of respiratory virus infections was reduced by 7.7% (95% CI 3.7% to 11.8%, P = 0.00018) and in children by 14.2% (95% CI 7.3% to 21.1%, P = 0.000053) [2: Analysis 2.1].

In another meta-analysis of 12 controlled trials, vitamin C shortened the duration of ICU stay on average by 7.8% (95% CI: 4.2% to 11.2%; P = 0.00003) [3]. In a third meta-analysis, vitamin C was

1 Harri Hemilä, MD, PhD

Department of Public Health, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, FINLAND.

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/en/persons/harri-hemil%C3%A4>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

most beneficial for critical care patients with the longest mechanical ventilation, corresponding to the most severely ill patients. In 5 controlled trials including 471 patients requiring ventilation for over 10 h, a dosage of 1–6 g/day of vitamin C shortened ventilation time on average by 25% ($P < 0.0001$) [4].

A recent RCT observed that vitamin C increased the recovery rate of outpatient cases of SARS-CoV-2 infection by 70% [5,6]. Another recent RCT found that vitamin C decreased mortality of sepsis patients in the period up to day 4 with $RR = 0.19$ (95% CI 0.06-0.55), but had no effect from day 5 onwards. Compared to the statistical model with no vitamin C effect over the 28-day period, the two-period model improved the Cox regression with $P = 0.002$ [7,8].

Hydroxychloroquine may be ineffective as a prophylaxis to prevent SARS-CoV-2. However, vitamin C is not a valid placebo. Using vitamin C as a placebo might lead to a false negative conclusions about hydroxychloroquine.

References

1. Barnabas RV, Brown ER, Bershteyn A, Stankiewicz Karita HC, Johnston C, Thorpe LE, Kottkamp A, Neuzil KM, Laufer MK, Deming M, Paasche-Orlow MK, Kissinger PJ, Luk A, Paolino K, Landovitz RJ, Hoffman R, Schaafsma TT, Krows ML, Thomas KK, Morrison S, Haugen HS, Kidoguchi L, Wener M, Greninger AL, Huang ML, Jerome KR, Wald A, Celum C, Chu HY, Baeten JM. Hydroxychloroquine as Postexposure Prophylaxis to Prevent Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 Infection : A Randomized Trial. *Ann Intern Med.* 2020 Dec 8:M20-6519. <https://doi.org/10.7326/m20-6519>
<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc7732017>
2. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD000980.pub4>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8078152>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225864>
3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu11040708>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6521194>
4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40560-020-0432-y>
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7006137>
5. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2021.0369>
6. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34040614>
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2021.674681>
7. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2019.11825>
8. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33117837>
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2020.590853>